

THE EXPANDED SERIES OF MULTIPLE HARMONIC SUMS AND MULTIPLE ZETA VALUES

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Abstract

In this paper, we introduce an explicit expanded series for multiple zeta values. The series is rapidly convergent and defined in a wide region. Additionally, the series yields innumerable identities.

1 Notation

1. Define the multiple zeta value as

$$\begin{aligned}\zeta(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_m) &:= \sum_{0 < k_m < k_{m-1} < \dots < k_1} \frac{1}{k_1^{\alpha_1} k_2^{\alpha_2} \dots k_m^{\alpha_m}} \\ &= \sum_{k_m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{k_{m-1}=k_m+1}^{\infty} \dots \sum_{k_1=k_2+1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k_1^{\alpha_1} k_2^{\alpha_2} \dots k_m^{\alpha_m}}.\end{aligned}$$

In the same way, define the right finite multiple zeta value as

$$\begin{aligned}\zeta_q(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_m) &:= \sum_{0 < k_m < k_{m-1} < \dots < k_1 \leq q} \frac{1}{k_1^{\alpha_1} k_2^{\alpha_2} \dots k_m^{\alpha_m}} \\ &= \sum_{k_m=1}^q \sum_{k_{m-1}=k_m+1}^q \dots \sum_{k_1=k_2+1}^q \frac{1}{k_1^{\alpha_1} k_2^{\alpha_2} \dots k_m^{\alpha_m}}\end{aligned}$$

and define the left finite multiple zeta value as

$$\begin{aligned}{}_q\zeta(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_m) &:= \sum_{q < k_m < k_{m-1} < \dots < k_1} \frac{1}{k_1^{\alpha_1} k_2^{\alpha_2} \dots k_m^{\alpha_m}} \\ &= \sum_{k_m=q+1}^{\infty} \sum_{k_{m-1}=k_m+1}^{\infty} \dots \sum_{k_1=k_2+1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k_1^{\alpha_1} k_2^{\alpha_2} \dots k_m^{\alpha_m}}.\end{aligned}$$

And, $\zeta_q(\alpha_k, \dots, \alpha_{k-1}) := 1$, ${}_q\zeta(\alpha_k, \dots, \alpha_{k-1}) := 1$.

2. $\{\alpha\}^m := \underbrace{(\alpha, \dots, \alpha)}_m$.

3. Define difference operator as

$$\Delta_q[f(q)] := f(q+1) - f(q).$$

4. $S_{1\text{st}}(\alpha)$ denotes the unsigned stirling number of the first kind.

5. For an index $\mathbb{A} := (\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_m)$, $\mathbb{A}_{[j]} := (\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_j)$ and $\mathbb{A}^{[j]} := (\alpha_{j+1}, \dots, \alpha_m)$.

6. For an admissible index $\mathbb{A}$, define its dual index as $\mathbb{A}^\dagger$.

2 The MZV Expansion Formula

Theorem 2.1. (The MZV Expansion Formula) with $\text{Re}(\alpha_1) > 1$ and $q \notin \mathbb{Z}_{<0}$, it follows;

$$\zeta(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_m) - \zeta_q(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_m) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \sum_{j=1}^m \frac{A_{j,k} \zeta_q(\alpha_{j+1}, \dots, \alpha_m)}{k + \alpha_1 - 1} \frac{q!}{(q + k + \alpha_1 - 1)!},$$

$$\text{where } \forall x, \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} A_{j+1,k} \frac{x!}{(x + k + \alpha_1)!} = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{A_{j,k}}{(x+1)^{\alpha_{j+1}-1} (k + \alpha_1 - 1)} \frac{x!}{(x + k + \alpha_1)!} \quad (1 \leq j \leq m-1),$$

$$A_{1,k} = S_{1\text{st}} \binom{k + \alpha_1 - 1}{\alpha_1 - 1} = (k + \alpha_1 - 2)! \zeta_{k+\alpha_1-2}(\{1\}^{\alpha_1-2}).$$

Proof. Calculating both sides with difference operator will prove that. First, the left side is,

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_q [\zeta(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_m) - \zeta_q(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_m)] &= -\Delta_q [\zeta_q(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_m)] \\ &= -\sum_{k_m=1}^{q+1} \sum_{k_{m-1}=k_m+1}^{q+1} \cdots \sum_{k_1=k_2+1}^{q+1} \frac{1}{k_1^{\alpha_1} k_2^{\alpha_2} \cdots k_m^{\alpha_m}} \\ &\quad + \sum_{k_m=1}^q \sum_{k_{m-1}=k_m+1}^q \cdots \sum_{k_1=k_2+1}^q \frac{1}{k_1^{\alpha_1} k_2^{\alpha_2} \cdots k_m^{\alpha_m}} \\ &= -\frac{\zeta_q(\alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_m)}{(q+1)^{\alpha_1}}. \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Second, the right side is,

$$\begin{aligned} &\Delta_q \left[\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \sum_{j=1}^m \frac{A_{j,k} \zeta_q(\alpha_{j+1}, \dots, \alpha_m)}{k + \alpha_1 - 1} \frac{q!}{(q + k + \alpha_1 - 1)!} \right] \\ &= -\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \zeta_q(\alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_m) S_{1\text{st}} \binom{k + \alpha_1 - 1}{\alpha_1 - 1} \frac{q!}{(q + k + \alpha_1)!} \\ &\quad - \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \sum_{j=1}^{m-1} \left(A_{j+1,k} - \frac{A_{j,k}}{(k + \alpha_1 - 1)(q+1)^{\alpha_{j+1}-1}} \right) \zeta_q(\alpha_{j+2}, \dots, \alpha_m) \frac{q!}{(q + k + \alpha_1)!} \\ &= -\frac{\zeta_q(\alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_m)}{(q+1)^{\alpha_1}} - \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \sum_{j=1}^{m-1} \left(A_{j+1,k} - \frac{A_{j,k}}{(k + \alpha_1 - 1)(q+1)^{\alpha_{j+1}-1}} \right) \zeta_q(\alpha_{j+2}, \dots, \alpha_m) \frac{q!}{(q + k + \alpha_1)!}. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Comparing (1) and (2), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \zeta(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_m) - \zeta_q(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_m) &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \sum_{j=1}^m \frac{A_{j,k} \zeta_q(\alpha_{j+1}, \dots, \alpha_m)}{k + \alpha_1 - 1} \frac{q!}{(q + k + \alpha_1 - 1)!} \\ \Leftrightarrow \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} A_{j+1,k} \frac{q!}{(q + k + \alpha_1)!} &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{A_{j,k}}{(q+1)^{\alpha_{j+1}-1} (k + \alpha_1 - 1)} \frac{q!}{(q + k + \alpha_1)!} \quad (1 \leq j \leq m-1), \\ A_{1,k} &= S_{1\text{st}} \binom{k + \alpha_1 - 1}{\alpha_1 - 1}. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore we have

$$\Delta_q [\zeta(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_m) - \zeta_q(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_m)] = \Delta_q \left[\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \sum_{j=1}^m \frac{A_{j,k} \zeta_q(\alpha_{j+1}, \dots, \alpha_m)}{k + \alpha_1 - 1} \frac{q!}{(q + k + \alpha_1 - 1)!} \right] \quad (3)$$

and

$$\lim_{q \rightarrow \infty} \zeta(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_m) - \zeta_q(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_m) = \lim_{q \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \sum_{j=1}^m \frac{A_{j,k} \zeta_q(\alpha_{j+1}, \dots, \alpha_m)}{k + \alpha_1 - 1} \frac{q!}{(q + k + \alpha_1 - 1)!} = 0. \quad (4)$$

The theorem follows from (3) and (4). $\square$

Lemma 2.1. *In Theorem 2.1, it follows;*

$$\Delta_q[f_{q,j+1}(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_{j+1})] = -\frac{1}{(q+1)^{\alpha_{j+1}}} f_{q+1,j}(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_j), \quad f_{q,1}(\alpha_1) = {}_q\zeta(\alpha_1) \quad (1 \leq j \leq m-1),$$

$$\text{where } f_{q,j}(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_j) := \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{A_{j,k}}{k + \alpha_1 - 1} \frac{q!}{(q+k+\alpha_1-1)!}.$$

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} & \Delta_q \left[\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{A_{j+1,k}}{k + \alpha_1 - 1} \frac{q!}{(q+k+\alpha_1-1)!} \right] \\ &= - \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} A_{j+1,k} \frac{q!}{(q+k+\alpha_1)!} \\ &= - \frac{1}{(q+1)^{\alpha_{j+1}}} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{A_{j,k}}{(k + \alpha_1 - 1)} \frac{(q+1)!}{(q+k+\alpha_1)!}. \end{aligned}$$

And it follows that $f_{q,1}(\alpha_1) = \zeta(\alpha_1) - \zeta_q(\alpha_1) = {}_q\zeta(\alpha_1)$ from Theorem 2.1. □

Lemma 2.2. *It follows;*

$$f_{q,j}(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_j) = {}_q\zeta(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_j).$$

Proof. ${}_q\zeta(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_j)$ satisfies the recurrence relation of Lemma 2.1. □

Theorem 2.2. *There holds;*

$$\zeta(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_m) = \sum_{k=1}^{m+1} {}_q\zeta(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_{k-1}) \zeta_q(\alpha_k, \dots, \alpha_m).$$

Proof. It follows from Theorem 2.1 and Lemma 2.2. □

Conjecture 2.1. *Define $\mathbb{A}_j := (\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_j)$ and $(\mathbb{A}_j)_{(k)} := \alpha_k$, then*

$$A_{j,k} = \frac{(k + \alpha_1 - 2)!}{(k + \alpha_1 - 1)^{((\mathbb{A}_j)^\dagger)_{(1)} - 2}} \zeta_{k+\alpha_1-2}(((\mathbb{A}_j)^\dagger)^{[1]}).$$

Theorem 2.3. *Conjecture 2.1 $\Rightarrow$ Duality.*

Proof. In Lemma 2.1 and 2.2, substituting 0 for q, we get

$$\zeta(\mathbb{A}) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{\zeta_{k+\alpha_1-2}((\mathbb{A}^\dagger)^{[1]})}{(k + \alpha_1 - 1)^{(\mathbb{A}^\dagger)_{(1)}}} = \zeta(\mathbb{A}^\dagger).$$

□

The expansion formula can be applied for many uses. We have a few examples;

Example 2.1. (*One-Height Duality*) with $1 < \alpha$,

$$\zeta(\alpha, \{1\}^m) = \zeta(m+2, \{1\}^{\alpha-2}).$$

Proof. In theorem 2.1, applying $(q, \alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_{m+1}) \rightarrow (1, \alpha, 1, \dots, 1)$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \zeta(\alpha, \{1\}^m) &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{S_{1st} \binom{k+\alpha-1}{\alpha-1}}{(k+\alpha-1)^{m+1} (k+\alpha-1)!} \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(k+\alpha-2)! \zeta_{k+\alpha-2}(\{1\}^{\alpha-2})}{(k+\alpha-1)^{m+1} (k+\alpha-1)!} \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{\zeta_{k+\alpha-2}(\{1\}^{\alpha-2})}{(k+\alpha-1)^{m+2}} \\ &= \zeta(m+2, \{1\}^{\alpha-2}). \end{aligned}$$

□

Example 2.2. with $1 < \alpha_1$,

$$\zeta(\alpha_1, \alpha_2) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{S_{1st} \binom{j+\alpha_1-1}{\alpha_1-1}}{k^{\alpha_2} (j+\alpha_1-1)} \frac{k!}{(k+j+\alpha_1-1)!}.$$

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} \zeta_q(\alpha_1, \alpha_2) &= \sum_{k=1}^q \frac{\zeta_q(\alpha_1) - \zeta_k(\alpha_1)}{k^{\alpha_2}} \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^q \frac{(\zeta(\alpha_1) - \zeta_k(\alpha_1)) - (\zeta(\alpha_1) - \zeta_q(\alpha_1))}{k^{\alpha_2}} \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^q \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{S_{1st} \binom{j+\alpha_1-1}{\alpha_1-1}}{k^{\alpha_2} (j+\alpha_1-1)} \left(\frac{k!}{(k+j+\alpha_1-1)!} - \frac{q!}{(q+j+\alpha_1-1)!} \right) \end{aligned}$$

Let $q \rightarrow \infty$, we obtain

$$\zeta(\alpha_1, \alpha_2) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{S_{1st} \binom{j+\alpha_1-1}{\alpha_1-1}}{k^{\alpha_2} (j+\alpha_1-1)} \frac{k!}{(k+j+\alpha_1-1)!}.$$

□

For instance,

Example 2.3.

$$\zeta(2, \alpha) = \sum_{k_1=1}^{\infty} \sum_{k_2=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k_1^{\alpha-1} k_2} \frac{(k_1-1)!(k_2-1)!}{(k_1+k_2)!}.$$

Example 2.4.

$$\zeta(3, \alpha) = \sum_{k_1=1}^{\infty} \sum_{k_2=1}^{\infty} \frac{\zeta_{k_2}(1)}{k_1^{\alpha} (k_2+1)} \frac{k_1! k_2!}{(k_1+k_2+1)!}.$$

References

- [1] Hanamichi Kawamura, Takumi Maesaka, Shin-ichiro Seki *Multivariable connected sums and multiple polylogarithms.* [arXiv](#)

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